

EXPERIENCES TOWARDS EVIDENCE-BASED POLICY FOR OPEN SCIENCE

This document has been produced by the members of the Working Group: “Evidence-Based Open Science Policies”, emerging from the CERN-NASA Summit in July 2023.

Research institutions around the world are increasingly developing open science policies, strategies and action plans. Following this momentum, the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science provides common ground in terms of the definition and key areas that institutions should consider when promoting open science.

After the 2023 CERN-NASA Summit “Accelerating the Adoption of Open Science”, a group of participants highlighted the need for institutions to consider an evidence-based approach to open science policy. The experts understand that **it is necessary to reach consensus on a framework for assessing the impact of open science policies**, as a first step towards an evidence-based policy approach.

The goal of the case studies presented here is to highlight how institutions around the world are approaching the topic of monitoring the impact of their open science programs and policies. This work is intended to inform research institutions of some opportunities and strategies for monitoring the implementation of open science. It intends to add to and complement other efforts in this field, such as the UNESCO Working Group on Monitoring Open Science, or the [Open Science Monitoring Initiative](#).

EXPERIENCES OVERVIEW

The three experiences we present here illustrate how different institutions, at different scales, are approaching the topic:

- **Research institution:** *the Open Science Office at the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)*
- **Network of institutions:** *the Open Research Programme at the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)*
- **National level:** *Open Science at the National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)*

We first present a summary of each case, followed by more detailed case studies.

UKRN

The UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) is spearheading efforts to enhance open research practices across UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). A recent survey conducted among member institutions identified priorities for an upcoming open research monitoring pilot.

The principles guiding open research indicators emphasize sector-led initiatives, interoperability, transparency, and data accessibility. Findings from the survey reveal diverse priorities across institutions, with clusters such as sharing research data, FAIR research, open access to publications, and training and awareness emerging as key areas of focus.

The pilot project, involving 14 member institutions, targets four main areas for monitoring: FAIR data, data availability statements, pre-registration, and the use of the CRediT taxonomy. Institutions are paired with solution providers, including both academic and commercial entities, to implement monitoring initiatives. However, concerns arise regarding the exclusion of smaller, more academic-led initiatives, which may limit diversity and innovation within the monitoring community.

EMBL

The EMBL Open Science Policy aims to enhance societal benefits from EMBL's scientific endeavors by promoting openness, transparency, and the publication of research articles, software, and data. This policy is facilitated by the Office for Scientific Information Management (OSIM), established in 2022 in Germany, which oversees various aspects such as the EMBL Szilárd Library, Archive, and Records Management.

Monitoring the impact of the Open Science Policy presents challenges due to the lack of specific assessment provisions in the policy itself. EMBL employs open infrastructure and minimal, sustainable tools for monitoring, primarily focusing on open access compliance, open data, and open-source software.

Initial findings from quantitative monitoring indicate high rates of preprints and open access articles, with improvements observed over time since policy implementation. However, challenges remain, particularly regarding data management plan uptake. Efforts are underway to address these challenges, including capacity building and improving implementation guidelines.

Monitoring efforts also aim to assess broader impacts through qualitative data, such as on equity, diversity, inclusion, collaborations, and societal outcomes. EMBL is exploring various methods, including web-based guides, improved metadata linking, and early intervention in training to enhance the effectiveness of the policy.

China is one of the largest contributors of scientific articles, hosting in 2022 the [highest number of most cited papers](#) according to a report by Japan's National Institute of Science and Technology Policy (NISTEP). After the publication of the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation in 2021, the Chinese Government boosted national open science commitments.

To assess China's readiness in adopting open science, the Open Science team at CAS proposed an "Open Science Readiness Index". This index considers factors such as open access, open data, and open policies to evaluate the country's progress in open science implementation.

Findings from a study at CAS indicate that China has implemented open science practices across various domains outlined in the UNESCO Recommendation. However, there are gaps in fostering open science culture, policy coordination, and capacity building.

Recommendations for advancing open science in China include increasing the volume of open access publications, improving data quality and integrity, enhancing legal and financial capabilities, and engaging in global open science governance.

Challenges identified in implementing these recommendations include high article processing charges (APCs), limited STEM data platforms, and a lack of research on open science policy.

FULL TEXT CASE STUDIES: CASE STUDY 1

Open Science monitoring practices at EMBL

With 29 member states, the [European Molecular Biology Laboratory \(EMBL\)](#) has more than 110 independent research groups and service teams covering the spectrum of molecular biology. The EMBL Open Science Policy, introduced in December 2021, focuses on open access to publications, research data, and software in line with FAIR principles.

Background

The EMBL Open Science Policy aims to improve societal outcomes from EMBL's scientific programme through openness, transparency, and the open publication of results in the form of research articles, software and data.

The Office for Scientific Information Management (OSIM) at EMBL was established in 2022, bringing together the EMBL Szilárd Library, EMBL Archive, and EMBL Records Management into a unified team.

The primary remit of EMBL's open science policy is open research; other initiatives include reforming research assessment, a program and strategy for equality, diversity, and inclusion, and many activities in science, education, and public engagement. Although these projects are very important aspects of open science, currently only the open research aspect is formally attached to EMBL's open science policy.

Domains of EMBL's open science policy (source: EMBL Open Science Office)

The goals in the first two years of the Open Science Policy implementation were a) to achieve EMBL-wide awareness of the Open Science Policy and OSIM's Open Science support; b) to incorporate the Open Science Policy into the publication workflow; and c) to monitor and achieve increasing adoption of Open Science practices at EMBL. The policy aims to inspire the research community to embrace best practices voluntarily, rather than enforcing compliance or imposing difficult requirements.

Open research monitoring at EMBL

The monitoring framework established in practice has four main goals: to internally inform leadership, to support iterative iterations of the strategy, to demonstrate momentum and therefore generate incentives, and to share lessons learned with the broader research community.

A key challenge when thinking about monitoring the open science policy impact is that the policy itself doesn't include provisions for assessment. Existing frameworks can be inspiring, but don't necessarily suit the internal institutional requirements. For example, EMBL only uses open infrastructure as a way of avoiding vendor lock-in. Another important restriction comes from the open science team having only one full-time officer, although EMBL is a large research organization.

Another challenge for monitoring was the internal publications workflow. Before the policy, all publications were handled by each research group or each research unit. This made it difficult to know how much EMBL was spending on APCs and how different groups were handling it. As part of the open science implementation, publications are now centralized, constituting a checkpoint for open access compliance. Researchers now have to go through the open science office when paying APCs. This means the office can access granular information on data management plans, preprints, open data and open software associated with the publication.

When dealing with publications where EMBL researchers are co-authors, EMBL works with librarians to track open access compliance. This work includes customized Python scripts and a do-it-yourself approach using Jupyter notebooks to avoid proprietary software. The goal is to keep tools minimal and sustainable in the long run, with a low technical demand.

Open Science Policy Monitoring framework

Open science monitoring framework at EMBL (source: EMBL Open Science Office)

Monitoring findings

Looking at publications in 2022, about 80% articles are available as preprints. In terms of open access articles, 87-90% are available open access as of this year; 81% consistently with a CC-BY license and 72-70% with full text deposit into our institutional repository. EMBL started collecting data in 2022; the numbers come from projects that have been running for five, six years prior to the policy coming into place.

Data from the Open Science observatory by OpenAIRE shows that 45.6% of publications in Europe are open access, one strong point for EMBL. Regarding open data, EMBL observed 78% compliance in the first year and 93% in the second year; while having 71% in open source software in the first year and 92-90% in the second year. There was a significant increase of about 20% in open data release since the implementation of the policy.

EMBL is also interested in detecting long-term trends in the adoption of these open science practices, beyond policy implementation. The office extrapolates publication and open access data over a couple of years, to detect if there's any real step increase or effect as a consequence of the policy intervention.

Data management plans are a weaker point. The uptake of data management plans is only 36%, which triggered a collaboration with EMBL data science centers and training to put more effort into a data management plan capacity building in 2023. Diving into the root causes of this number, the office realized that the implementation guidelines they produced were in a 15-page document that only a few people read.

A first approach to evidence-based open research

The results of monitoring efforts are already informing EMBL's actions in open science. Regarding the uptake of data management plans, there is now a community-based effort to digest the implementation guidelines into a more easily approachable web-based guide.

They also aim to improve the monitoring infrastructure itself. Currently, 50% of EMBL's preprints that the office is aware of are connected to journal publications; metadata linking is very much lacking. EMBL is currently working to build better workflows to use raw IDs and other tools to improve the monitoring infrastructure as a result.

Finally, a key learning is that implementation needs earlier intervention. The results observed today are papers that have started three, four years ago; in many cases that's too late. They are now identifying all the points where open science training can be incorporated early on in the research process.

Quantitative indicators are only half of the equation when it comes to open science. At EMBL it is key to understand how the open science policy impacts the research community in a broader sense. The impact of the equity, diversity and inclusion program, or the prominence of collaboration networks, are some examples. Researchers at EMBL often collaborate with member states and other non-member state countries. There is data on these collaborations since 2019, that the office aims to use to understand how this collaboration network has evolved over the last few years, especially with the adoption of the open science policy.

Another key area for EMBL monitoring efforts is impact in society. One idea for approaching this broad dimension is to monitor patent databases and the impact of the open science policy in technology transfer activity. This is still in development, as well as monitoring of capacity building activities. Now that open science training is embedded into all of the key identified areas, qualitative information can provide insights on how trained personnel work and how they continue to adopt open science practices after training.

FULL TEXT CASE STUDIES: CASE STUDY 2

Identifying priorities for open research monitoring in UK Higher Education Institutions (UKRN)

The UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) is a peer-led consortium whose vision is for the UK research system to be outstanding in conducting and promoting rigorous and transparent research. The UKRN Open Research Programme has recently published a working paper summarizing the results of a recent survey to member institutions, on priorities for a near future open research monitoring pilot.

Background

The UKRN leads a multi-year Open Research Programme to promote the uptake of open research practices across the UK sector, including training, revisions to institutional recognition and reward policies and procedures, sharing practice among institutions, and monitoring / evaluating progress against our aims.

It has committed to provide and assess solutions such as dashboards and reporting tools to institutions, to help them plan, deliver and evaluate the effectiveness of their support for open research practices.

Pilot projects are planned in 14 institutions that are members of UKRN, to explore the potential and value of indicators of open research to inform how those institutions plan, implement and evaluate their support for open research. As a first

stage of this work, a [recent report](#) publishes the results of a survey identifying priorities in open research monitoring for those institutions.

The surveyed institutions are:

- University of Bristol
- Cardiff University
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Exeter
- University of Glasgow
- University of Hull
- King's College London
- University of Leeds
- University of Leicester
- University of Liverpool
- Newcastle University
- University of Reading
- University of Sheffield
- University of Sussex

Principles of open research indicators

Open research indicators are aggregate and anonymous, differentiating them from researcher-based assessments that are often the scope of incentives discussions. The goal is to use these indicators to assess implementation of open research policies, and plan strategies that are effective for each institution.

UKRN has identified the main principles that open research indicators should comply with:

- **Sector-led:** driven by the priorities of the UK research sector, before any consideration of which systems, solutions, or providers might be relevant to them.
- **Interoperability and solution neutrality:** All partners are free to use their own or third-party products and services. All partners will make all reasonable efforts to ensure optimal interoperability for their data and services.
- **Transparency, inclusion, and collaboration:** Aim to make science and research more transparent, efficient, inclusive, openly and freely accessible, and collaborative.
- **Access to research data and metadata:** Preference will be given to solutions that both exploit and contribute to:
 - FAIR and open sector-wide / system-wide data
 - Institutional data about research, to render solutions that are – as far as possible – context-sensitive and unsuitable for rankings.
- **Data portability:** All partners agree that any data they choose to share as part of this work can be freely transferred by others to their own or to a third-party host environment

Findings: priorities for monitoring

An early “call for priorities” asked institutions to propose up to five aspects of open research as being their priorities. A total of 29 responses were received, which identified 83 discrete priorities.

A total of 21 institutions were represented in the responses. Many of the aspects of open research indicated several discrete priorities and so, when disaggregated there were 38 discrete priorities from organizations and 45 from

individuals, making a total of [83 discrete priorities](#).

The main, broad clusters identifiable from this exercise are as follows:

- **Sharing research data**
- **Sharing research software**
- **FAIR research**
- **Open Access to publications**
- **Open research beyond publications**
- **The use of persistent identifiers**
- **Metadata and technical standards**
- **Links across the scholarly record**
- **Pre-registration**
- **Reward and recognition**
- **Training and awareness**
- **Equality, diversity and inclusion**

The main stakeholders cited as likely to be affected were researchers and professional support staff directly supporting open research. 'Affected' could mean many things, including benefiting from monitoring these aspects of open research, or perhaps incurring risks or costs, or having changed working practices or relationships.

A first approach to monitoring and challenges

After reviewing the priorities, the pilot institutions agreed to focus on the following four areas:

OPEN / FAIR DATA	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The FAIRness of data● The Openness of data● Effects of sharing data
DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The prevalence of adequate Data Availability Statements● Quality and reliability of Data Availability Statements
PRE-REGISTRATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The Prevalence of Preregistration
USE OF CRediT TAXONOMY	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● The overall use of the CRediT taxonomy● How are CRediT records being populated?

In order to implement monitoring, institutions are paired with “solution providers”. These are teams who might be willing and able to work with institutions and UKRN to pilot the indicators. The call for solution providers produced a range of initiatives, from small academic-led projects to large commercial operations.

The final selection of solution providers include the Centre for Open Science, CORE, Digital Science, Elsevier, OpenAIRE and PLOS / DataSeer.

The exclusion of smaller, more academic-led, often more open source initiatives is a concern. It is likely to have arisen for a number of reasons, including a) lack of funding for the pilots, which favors large operations who can afford delayed pay back; b) institutions seem to favor partners who can offer staff time, a level of brand recognition and familiarity, and large datasets.

These factors pose a high barrier to entry, and may reduce the diversity within the innovation community. It also calls attention to the opportunities and risks of sourcing indicators relating to its core business from third parties, and how those might be managed to benefit research.

FULL TEXT CASE STUDIES: CASE STUDY 3

Informing national strategy through the “Open Science Readiness Index”

China is one of the largest contributors of scientific articles globally. After the publication of the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation in 2021, the Chinese Government boosted national open science commitments. The National Science Library in the Chinese Academy of Sciences is in charge of monitoring national efforts on open science.

Background

Following the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, in China the “Law of the People’s Republic of China on Progress of Science and Technology” was amended for the second time on December 24, 2021 and came into force in January 2022, with the goal of “promoting the development of open science”.

However, open science activities can be traced back to 2003. These include Open Access policy initiatives, repositories, open publishing, preprints, open data, open infrastructure, open science training, and more.

The project "Research on the Trends and Impacts of Open Science" was initiated by the Academic Divisions of the Chinese Academy of Sciences. It focuses on open access, open data, and open science governance, as well as the current development status in China. The project aims to analyze the critical issues in open science governance and priority, proposing a roadmap and action plan for advancing open science in China.

The Chinese Open Science Network (COSN) was initiated in 2016. COSN has grown from a small Open Science interest group to a broad network in China. So far, COSN has organized three in-person workshops, 12 tutorials, 48 talks, and 55 journal club sessions and translated 15 Open Science-related articles and blogs from English to Chinese. Currently, the main social media account of COSN has more than 23,000 subscribers, and more than 1,000 researchers/students actively participate in the discussions on Open Science.

In terms of open access of publications, China contributes approximately 25% of the total according to SCIE data. In 2022, authors from China Mainland paid 650 M\$ to OA journals for APC, up 43% from 2021. NSFC supported half of them. China is the world's second-largest contributor to scientific dataset releases, making up 73% of the quantity released by the United States from 2012 to 2021, according to the Dimensions platform.

China currently has 20 scientific data centers, 12 preprint platforms established in various fields and the development of PubScholar (Public Academic Resource Platform). The platform, launched in November 2023, provides services such as search and discovery of public academic resources, content access, and communication and sharing.

Principles of open research indicators

The first step to plan a national strategy at CAS was to establish how well China is positioned in terms of open science adoption. This also provided information on which pathways are available for better alignment with the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation.

To do this, a recent study at CAS considers that research can be classified in four quadrants regarding its inclusiveness and openness, and that governments should aim to foster quadrant 1: Global Science, Commonwealth-driven. It also proposes the use of an “Open Science Readiness Index”, which takes into account three domains of open science: Open Access, Open Data and Open Policies.

The index weighs in these three domains as follows:

Open access	Global quantity and proportion of OA publications
	Global quantity and proportion of internationally collaborative research papers
Open data	Academic quality of data (number of scholar in top 1% for high citation FWCI)
	Information quality (FAIR principles)
	Integrity quality (retraction rate)
Open policy and governance	Legal and contractual protections
	Policy frameworks

Findings

Based on the collection of 149 open science practices from the Chinese scientific community in October 2022 (since 2002), CAS observes China has implemented open science practices across all seven action areas outlined in the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation.

Limitations include a shortage of initiatives fostering open science culture and promoting innovative approaches. Another notable gap can be found in exploring diverse paths in open science, creating a conducive policy environment,

coordinating incentives for open science, and investing in human resources and capacity building for open science.

The mentioned study applies the Open Science Readiness Index to various countries, including China. Results are shown in the graph below.

Dynamic curves of the open science maturity index corresponding to the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan, EU 27 countries, China, India, Russia, and STLCs (source: [Yang et al., 2023](#)).

A first approach to evidence-based policy

Based on these results, the team at the National Libraries-CAS has proposed recommendations to advance open science implementation at the national level.

These include:

- Increasing the share and volume of open access and internationally collaborative academic outputs,
- Improving the quality, information integrity, and reliability of research results with shareable data,
- Strengthening legal, infrastructure, and financial capabilities for accessible data,
- Engaging in global open science governance to continuously enhance the competitiveness of national open science policies.

However, the team has also detected potential challenges undermining these plans. In terms of open access, a key obstacle can be found in the price of APCs. In China, about five thousand domestic journals would need an open access model; this raises the question of how to financially support a sustainable model. In open data, a lack of STEM data platforms currently limits what can be achieved by researchers. Finally, the lack of open science policy research means that there is need for more information to better assess national strategies.

Proposed roadmap for open science policies in China (source: NLS at CAS)

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